

NOUN IN RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract: The article compares the noun in the Russian and English languages according to the method of formation and areas of use.

Key words: English language, Russian language, noun, language system, methods of word formation.

A noun is a significant part of speech that designates an object and expresses this meaning in the non-verbal category of gender and inflectional categories of number and case. Nouns are one of the most important parts of speech and make up almost half of all words in the Russian language.

The morphological categories of gender, number and case, characteristic of nouns in the Russian language, have long attracted the attention of both Russian linguists and their foreign colleagues (Pavsky R.P. - 1850; Potebnya A.A. - 1899; Sobolevsky A.I. - 1892-93; Bogoroditsky V.A. - 1935; Vostokov A.H. - 1831; Kurilovich E. - 1962; Madoyan V.V. - 1989; Peterson M.N. - 1955; Cheshko E.V. - 1960 ; Jacobson R.O.-1985).

We observed where difficulties most often arise when composing a sentence in English, as well as when translating a sentence from Russian into English. During our observation, it turned out that very often students forget to put an article before a word, both in written and oral speech.

Namely nouns name objects. Objects in grammar are called everything that you can ask about, who is this? who is this? or whatisthis? what is it? for example, aman is a person and an engineer is an engineer, and house is a house and work is work.

According to their generalized lexical meaning, nouns can be characterized as words denoting the names of objects, people, animals, plants, substances, phenomena and concepts, for example: a book, a student, a dog, a snake, a problem, water, a tree , bread. As in the Russian language, nouns in English according to their meaning are divided into proper and common

nouns, animate and inanimate, concrete and abstract, objective and material, countable and uncountable.

The formal features of nouns are the ability to express the grammatical categories of number, case and the semantic category of gender. These categories are almost the same in both languages, so we will consider only some of their features that are characteristic of the English language.

The division of nouns into proper and common nouns is similar to the corresponding division in Russian, except that proper nouns in English also include: 1) names of months and days of the week (January - январь; Sunday - воскресенье); 2) names of nationalities and national languages (the English - анличане; the English language - английский язык).

The number form of nouns (The Number).

One concept will be important for us - the division of nouns into countable and uncountable.

Countable nouns are names of concrete objects and abstract concepts that can be counted: an apple (one apple) - яблоко (одно яблоко); two, three, four... apples - два, три, четыре ... яблок. Countable nouns can have singular or plural forms. In the singular they may be preceded by an indefinite article.

Uncountable Nouns are names of substances, materials and concepts that do not have exact sizes and shapes, which therefore cannot be counted in units, for example: silver, snow, air, water, sand (серебро, снег, воздух, вода, песок), as well as: love, friendship, light ((любовь, дружба, свет). Uncountable nouns do not have a plural form and cannot be preceded by an indefinite article. When uncountable nouns take a plural form, they change their meaning. Wed: sands, waters, steels (пески, воды, сорта стали). The presence of an indefinite article before an uncountable noun gives it the meaning of portions.

For example:

- What are you having? – Что ты будешь?

- I shall have a Cola. - Я буду (одну) колу.

Functions of a noun in a sentence.

In a sentence, a noun can perform the following functions:

Subject

Life was slower in the 19th century.

В 19 веке жизнь была более размеренной.

Addition (direct, indirect, prepositional).

You did such splendid work.

They gave their son good advice.

Вы выполнили такую великолепную работу.

Они дали сыну хороший совет.

My son is a teacher.-Мой сын – учитель.

Circumstance

He found the car without difficulty.- Он нашел машину без труда.

She lives in the country.- Она живет за городом.

Application

His mother, a doctor, was a popular figure in the town.- Его мать, врач, была известной личностью в городе.

Gender in English

The category of gender in English is somewhat different from that in Russian. Genders in English are also divided into masculine, feminine and neuter, but words can only be assigned to one gender or another using context and knowledge of the lexical meaning of the word.

In English, as in Russian, nouns can be of three genders: masculine (Masculine), feminine (Feminine) and neuter (Neuter).

Masculine - Masculine

Animated male creatures. For example: : bridegroom (жених), son (сын), uncle (дядя), ox (бык).

Individual inanimate objects that, when personified, are classified as masculine. For example: Sun (солнце), wind (ветер), death (смерть), time (время).

Masculine words can be replaced by the personal pronoun he (he) and the possessive his (his), as in Russian.

Feminine - Feminine

This category of gender in English includes:

All animate beings are female. For example: girl (девушка), granny (бабушка), saleswoman (продавщица).

Ship names. Example: I saw the ship "Columbia". She is really wonderful! — Я видел корабль «Колумбия». Он (в английском «она») чудесен.

Individual inanimate objects that, when personified, are classified as feminine Earth (Земля), Moon (луна), boat (лодка), hope (надежда), peace (мир) and some others.

The feminine gender can sometimes be determined by the suffixes -ine, -ette, -ess

Examples: hostess (хозяйка), heroine (героиня).

Feminine words can be replaced by the personal pronoun she (she) and the possessive her (her).

Neuter - Neuter

This genus includes:

All inanimate objects and abstract concepts: table (стол), cup (чашка), picture (рисунок).

Animals, if there is no indication of its gender: cat (кот), wolf (волк), dog (собака).

Countries, if they are considered as geographical entities (if we consider a country as an economic and political entity, then it will be classified as feminine).

Neuter words can be replaced by the personal pronoun it (he, she, it) and the possessive its (his, her).

Features of the gender category in English

There are some words that can be classified as both masculine and feminine, depending on the context.

His sister is a teacher. — Его сестра учительница.

My father is a teacher. — Мой отец учитель.

Neighbor

This is my neighbour. He is friendly. — Это мой сосед. Он дружелюбный.

His neighbour is a friendly woman. — Его соседка дружелюбная женщина.

Cousin

My cousin is an eight-year-old boy. — Моему двоюродному брату 8 лет.

My cousin looks so beautiful in a blue dress. — Моя кузина выглядит прекрасно в голубом платье.

It happens that the gender of such a word cannot be determined by the context, then it belongs to an indeterminate gender (indeterminategender).

Examples: child (child), cook (cook), assistant (assistant), singer (singer).

If it is necessary to indicate gender, words can be added to the noun that directly indicate it: man (мужчина), woman (женщина), boy (мальчик/молодой человек), girl (девушка), male (мужской), female (женский).

Примеры: girlfriend (подруга), woman-translator (переводчица).

No, he is not my boyfriend, he is just a male friend. — Нет, он не мой парень. Он просто мой друг.

I have three female cousins and two male cousins. — У меня три кузины и два кузена.

In some works of art, mainly poetry or fairy tales, inanimate objects “come to life,” that is, they are endowed with qualities that in reality belong only to living beings. Thus, at the will of the author, they can change the neuter gender to masculine or feminine. For example, death can take a masculine form, and night can take a feminine form, but in ordinary speech both words belong to the neuter.

The category of gender in English does not affect the grammatical structure of a sentence and does not change the form of any parts of speech, except for the requirement that they be replaced by pronouns of the appropriate gender. That's why many people say that there is no gender in English.

The waiter is very prompt — официант очень расторопен

The waitress is very prompt — официантка очень расторопна

The lion roars in the night — лев рычит в ночи

The lioness roars in the night — львица рычит в ночи

These sentences refer to masculine and feminine people and animals, but this does not affect the grammatical structure of the sentence in any way.

Likewise, natural differences in gender of such pairs as brother - sister (брат — сестра), nephew - niece (племянник — племянница), king - queen (король — королева) are not reflected in the grammatical form of the words associated with them. However, gender is important when choosing pronouns to replace such nouns.

John is late — Джон опоздал

He is late — Он опоздал

Mary is late — Мэри опоздала

She is late — Она опоздала

The choice of pronoun depends on the type of noun that identifies who is being spoken about.

However, this distinction disappears when it comes to the plural.

John and Mary are late — Джон и Мэри опоздали

They are late — Они опоздали

John and David are late — Джон и Дэвид опоздали

They are late — Они опоздали

Mary and Jane are late — Мэри и Джейн опоздали

They are late — Они опоздали

Studying the Russian language and confident command of its norms is an effective means of cultural education of a person and introducing him to unshakable humanistic values, and this is especially important in the current difficult conditions. And what is the state of the language, what are its development trends, is there a need and opportunity to influence them - these are the actual problems of the language, especially since they closely relate to the Russian language

as the national language of the Russian people and the language of interethnic communication [4,133]

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